

Monitoring InfiniBand networks to react efficiently to congestion

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Abstract—Current high-performance interconnection networks for HPC and Data-Center systems incorporate mechanisms to prevent congestion from degrading network performance. Specifically, the popular InfiniBand specification defines a mechanism to reduce the injection rate of the traffic flows contributing to congestion. However, the efficiency of this mechanism depends on the values configured for certain parameters, that may be suitable for some congestion situations but not for others. Therefore, we think that these parameters should be reconfigured dynamically, based on accurate and updated information about the actual status of congestion. For that purpose, we have combined a light-weight platform monitoring tool (LIMITLESS) with the InfiniBand control software (OpenSM), so that the former provides the latter with enhanced knowledge about congestion to appropriately reconfigure the parameters driving the behavior of the congestion-control mechanism. Experiments performed in a real InfiniBand-based cluster confirm that this approach significantly reduces the number of wrong reactions to the congestion-control mechanism.

Index Terms—Interconnection networks, cluster, congestion control, traffic monitoring, InfiniBand

I. BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATION

High-speed and low-latency interconnection networks are necessary for modern High-Performance Computing (HPC) clusters and Data-centers to cope with the communication requirements of the demanding applications and services supported by these systems, otherwise, the network becomes the entire system bottleneck. One of the most successful high-performance interconnect technologies is the InfiniBand Architecture (IBA), widely deployed in many systems ranked in the Top500 list.

Network components based on the IBA specification (switches, host channel adapters - HCAs - and links) allow for building different topologies, such as Fat-Trees, Dragonflies or other low-diameter networks, extensively used in

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HPC systems and data centers. Both the discovery of the actual network topology and the configuration of a suitable routing are responsibility of a software entity called the subnet manager (SM), which not only controls these functionalities but several others. The most popular implementation of the SM is OpenSM, included in the OpenFabrics Software (OFS).

In more detail, when discovering the network topology, the SM assigns 16-bit addresses, denominated Local Identifiers (LIDs) to the network devices (i.e., HCAs and switches), and populates the routing tables at switches, based on the selected routing algorithm. Although IBA-based networks support oblivious and adaptive routing, in this work we focus on deterministic routing. Each network device also has a GUID (Global Unique Identifier), a 64-bit identifier assigned to each device within a subnet. GUIDs are independent of LIDs. The SM also reconfigures the network in runtime upon eventual changes, faults or problems.

However, even if the SM configures an efficient routing for the specific system topology, this may be still spoiled by congestion situations derived from the system applications intensely generating traffic that clogs the network (or parts of the network) when injected from the HCAs. As these situations are likely to end up degrading network (and so system) performance, the IBA specification defines a congestion-control (CC) mechanism [1] to throttle the injection of traffic flows when they are detected as contributors to a congestion situation (i.e., as *congesting flows*). This mechanism follows a closed-loop approach that can be summarized in the following steps:

- 1) The occupancy of the buffers at the switch ports is monitored: if this occupancy exceeds a given threshold, the corresponding output port enters the congestion state.
- 2) Any packet crossing a port in congestion state can be marked as congesting (based on a marking rate configured previously) by activating the FECN (Forward Explicit Congestion Notification) bit at the packet header.
- 3) When an HCA receives a FECN-marked packet, it sends back a notification packet with the BECN (Backward Explicit Congestion Notification) bit set, addressed to the source HCA of the FECN-marked packet.
- 4) Source HCAs receiving BECNs will throttle the injection rate of those traffic flows addressed to the HCAs sending those BECNs.

In more detail, each source HCA applies a specific *injection rate delay* (IRD) to separate the injection of packets addressed to a given destination HCA. Each HCA holds a congestion control table (CCT), that contains entries to store 128 pre-configured IRD values, sorted in ascending order. The initial values in this IRDs list can be defined by the user in the OpenSM configuration. The specific IRD applied at a source HCA to inject packets addressed to a given destination is defined by the *CCTI_Index*, which points to an entry in the CCT. Upon every BECN reception at a source HCA, the *CCTI_Index* for the destination HCA that sent the BECN is increased to point to an entry in the CCT with a higher value of the IRD. In this way the injection rate for that flow is throttled (i.e., lowered). The specific increase applied to the *CCTI_Index* upon every BECN reception is defined by the *CCTI_Increase* parameter. By contrast, a source HCA decreases the IRD for a given destination by decreasing the *CCTI_Index* every time a *Timer* expires and no BECNs have been received from that destination (which indicates that congestion is vanishing in the path to that destination, so the injection rate towards that destination should increase accordingly). When the *CCTI_Index* is 0 at a source HCA for a given destination, no IRD is applied to the injection of packets towards that destination, as the mechanism considers that congestion has disappeared in the path to that destination. The typical value for *CCTI_Increase* is 1, and this value never changes during runtime, so the *CCTI_Index* increases and decreases on a one-by-one basis, and so the IRD for a given destination varies slowly.

Unfortunately, the performance of the IBA CC mechanism strongly depends on the tuning of the parameters described above, which is a real challenge [1], [2]. Moreover, congestion is by nature very dynamic [3], as it may appear at some network point, later move to a different one, and so on. Hence, it is very complex to identify accurately and at any moment the flows contributing to a congestion situation. Even flows not contributing to congestion can be wrongly identified as congesting and so their injection is unnecessarily throttled (“*victim*” flows). All this leads to instabilities in the performance of networks using the IBA CC mechanism.

For these reasons, we think that configuring and tuning dynamically the IBA CC parameters, based on the information provided by certain IBA performance counters, would improve the efficiency of the CC mechanism. Specifically, in this work, we focus on the IBA performance counters used at HCAs to measure the congestion severity, specifically on *PortXmitWait*, which measures the number of hardware cycles spent by an HCA waiting to transmit packets due to insufficient credits in the next switch buffer, and on *PortXmitData*, that measures the number of bytes injected in the network from a given HCA.

To gather the information from these performance counters in runtime, a fine-grain monitoring tool can be used, and then sending the collected information to the OpenSM to update the IBA CC parameters. Specifically, we propose combining the operation of OpenSM with an existing lightweight monitoring tool called LIMITLESS [4], [5], a monitor that can work under near-to-second sampling rates and provides the current IBA

performance counter values. Basically, the idea of our proposal is that LIMITLESS collects metrics about communication volumes in the network through the IBA performance counters at network devices. Then, LIMITLESS provides OpenSM with a precise image of where congestion is originated in the network and the degree of its severity. Finally, OpenSM configures the source HCAs of congesting flows to dynamically and precisely adjust their injection rates.

Note that system monitoring for large-scale HPC platforms is a complex task, which becomes increasingly challenging as the scale and complexity of the infrastructure grow. Indeed, some system monitors like Ganglia [6], Nagios [7], among others, present different problems when used in HPC systems, and moreover, they are not adapted specifically to monitor InfiniBand networks. In contrast, a generic work for monitoring tools for large-scale systems, including applications for InfiniBand was presented in [8]. More recently, INAM [9] and [10] allow users to analyze and visualize the communication state in an InfiniBand network of 2000 nodes with a very low overhead at scale and using OpenSM. LIMITLESS, compared to other HPC monitor tools, exhibits a low monitoring overhead, is highly scalable, collects global system information, and natively implements InfiniBand monitoring. In this way, all this collected information can be exploited using OpenSM.

In this work, we have implemented our proposal in OpenSM and evaluated it in a real HPC cluster using an IBA-based network, specifically the cluster CELLIA, whose details can be found in Section III-A. We have extended the OpenSM source code to communicate with LIMITLESS and receive information about congestion, using the IBA performance counters from network devices. For the experimentation, we use the Netgauge and GPCNeT benchmarks, activating either the traditional IBA CC or the technique. Based on the results, we can conclude that our proposal outperforms the IBA CC when Netgauge and GPCNeT are running.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II describes our proposal to combine a monitoring system with congestion control. Section III describes the experiments carried out in the real IBA-based cluster mentioned above and analyzes the obtained results. Finally, some conclusions are drawn in Section IV.

II. COMBINING CONGESTION CONTROL AND FINE-GRAIN MONITORING

A. Monitoring architecture

In this work, LIMITLESS is used to constantly monitor the cluster, and to provide information about the current state of the network to the IBA OpenSM. The monitoring system consists of three different components that are organized in a hierarchical way to transmit the performance information from the nodes and HCAs to the main server and OpenSM. The architecture is based on a Tree-Based Overlay Network (TBON) and offers simplicity, scalability, and fault tolerance. The final stage of this process consists of storing the metrics in a database that permits to analyze and visualize the system status.

Fig. 1: LIMITLESS monitor captures the performance information from the compute nodes and sends it to our OpenSM implementation. OpenSM decides which nodes should reconfigure their CC parameters, and then the Subnet Manager executes those reconfigurations.

The main components of LIMITLESS are: *Daemon Monitor* (LDM), *Daemon Aggregator* (LDA) and *Daemon Server* (LDS), that can be seen in Figure 1. More relevant for this work, the LDM daemon periodically collects the information about the IBA performance counters (i.e., *PortXmitData*, *PortXmitWait*, etc.), and sends it to the OpenSM process to reconfigure the IBA CC parameters. The LDM is executed in every server node and queries the performance counters of the node’s IBA HCA. Each LDA (note that the number of LDAs depends on the monitor deployment) receives and transforms the data by applying compression (to reduce the network traffic) and re-transmits the information to the next monitoring component. The LDS receives, processes, and stores the collected metrics from the HCAs and shares them with OpenSM.

By means of LIMITLESS, it is possible to collect the performance metrics and re-configure the CC parameters of the whole cluster every 100ms. In order to measure the overhead produced by the LDMs (note that these are the monitor components executed in the compute nodes), we have collected the time that each LDM has been in execution and the average load that is reached. For each hour of execution, each LMD consumes 19.85s with an average load of 0.5% of CPU -which represents a reduced monitoring overhead-.

B. Dynamic reconfiguration of the IBA CC Parameters

As mentioned above, the system monitor collects and stores the HCAs performance counters using the LDS process that communicates with OpenSM in order to provide the collected data, which will be used to react when congestion appears.

Our proposal is focused on modifying the configuration of the IBA CC parameters at those HCAs that generate traffic flows that contribute to congestion, based on the information

provided by the monitor, and in a dynamic way. The reconfiguration consists in applying a more aggressive injection rate delay (IRD) to congesting flows in those HCAs, which permits efficient reactions to the network congestion and prevents its negative effects. To detect whether an HCA is contributing to congestion, we look at the *PortXmitWait* value provided by LIMITLESS to OpenSM for each HCA. This value counts the number of processor clock cycles that a specific HCA has to wait in order to inject traffic into the network. Therefore, large values indicate congestion. If this value exceeds the predefined *upper_limit* value (later explained), then the HCA is waiting too much, which is an early indicator to identify that this HCA might be contributing to congestion.

When a given HCA with a high *PortXmitWait* value is truly contributing to congestion, packets generated by this HCA will be marked, and sooner or later BECN notifications will be received. As OpenSM (in our proposal) updates the *CCTI_Increase* for that HCA, the *CCTI_Index* will be increased, so that the injection throttling will be applied in that HCA. However, high values for *PortXmitWait* can be observed in HCAs generating victim flows, which we do not want to throttle. Note that these HCAs will not take into account the BECN notifications received, so the injection throttling will not be enabled, which is an advantage for our proposal.

If the *PortXmitWait* value drops below a *lower_limit*, this is an indication that the IBA-CC is reacting and/or congestion is vanishing. At this moment, we set the *CCTI_Increase* parameter to zero, thus the injection throttling will be disabled in that HCA because *CCTI_Index* will not be incremented, and it will decrease to zero as the *Timer* expires repeatedly. This decision-making algorithm can be seen in Algorithm 1, which specifically shows how the reconfiguration is performed.

OpenSM configures the CC mechanism using the recommended values for the parameters [1], but with the *CCTI_Increase* parameter equal to zero. This means that the HCAs discard the received BECNs and no injection throttling is applied. Indeed, the CC is not enabled at HCAs until LIMITLESS reports the OpenSM that the *PortXmitWait* exceeds the *upper_limit*. Hence, OpenSM needs to check the *PortXmitWait* value for all the HCAs in the network, at the same rate as these values are provided by LIMITLESS. Note that any new configuration for the *CCTI_Increase* parameter of a given HCA (either to enable or disable that parameter) is sent by the OpenSM to that HCA, via management datagrams (MADs). Note that, due to the necessity of accelerating this part of the algorithm, the processes use shared mapped memory files, which allows the processes to read and write the shared file faster.

Besides, as another optimization to reduce potential unnecessary reconfigurations, OpenSM knows if the HCA has already been updated, so it is possible to avoid continuously sending MADs with the *CCTI_Increase* parameter configuration to the HCAs.

Algorithm 1 *CC_Update_HCAs* decides whether to update the CC parameters in the HCAs.

Input Parameters: upper_limit, lower_limit, ccti_new_value

```

1: for all HCAs in the Subnet do
2:   if (!cc_modified and
      port_xmit_wait > upper_limit) then
3:     cc_modified ← true
4:     ccti_increase ← ccti_new_value
5:     send_new_cc_conf_to_hca()
6:   end if
7:   if (cc_modified and
      port_xmit_wait < lower_limit) then
8:     cc_modified ← false
9:     ccti_increase ← 0
10:    send_default_cc_conf_to_hca()
11:  end if
12: end for

```

C. OpenSM implementation

This section describes the modifications made in the OpenSM v3.3.19 to implement our proposal. We have configured the network routing according to the well-known D -mod- K deterministic routing algorithm, which distributes evenly the routes among all the links connecting any two stages of the fat-tree, so achieving a performance similar to (or even better than) adaptive routing under several traffic scenarios while reducing implementation complexity¹. We have evaluated our proposal in a real cluster using an IBA-based network, where we have built a slimmed fat-tree (SFT) topology. We have included the source code of our proposal in the `ftree` routing engine available in OpenSM. Specifically, the `ftree` routing engine exchanges MADs with the IBA devices (i.e., the HCAs) by means of several functions provided by the OpenSM congestion control manager (*CCMgr*). The two main functions are `osm_ftree_send_ca_cong_setting` and `osm_ftree_mad_post`. The first one encapsulates the new values of the CC parameters in a MAD. The second one is used to send MADs to their corresponding HCA.

The monitor provides OpenSM with the performance counters information in a shared mapped memory file, updated periodically (approximately every sampling interval). This file has one line per node in the network. Each line contains the GUID, and the value of the IBA performance counters of the corresponding HCA. OpenSM needs to read and process this file faster than LIMITLESS collects the corresponding information. To read this information, the OpenSM `ftree` routing engine includes a function called `ftree_read_monitor`, which is run periodically. Note that this function is not executed every OpenSM sweep time, but it is run according to the monitor sampling interval (which is user-defined as a

¹Note however that our proposal is also compatible with (i.e., feasible in) networks using other routing algorithms, either deterministic or adaptive, although its actual efficiency may vary depending on the specific congestion dynamics derived from the different routings.

parameter to OpenSM). This function obtains the *PortXmitWait* value for all the HCAs in the network, and supply this information to another function, called `ftree_cc_update_hca` that implements the functionality described in Algorithm 1. This function decides if the CC parameters at a given HCA need to be updated.

III. EVALUATION RESULTS

In this section, we describe the proof-of-concept built to analyze the behavior of our proposal in a realistic testbed. Our main objective is to verify that the timely information provided by the LIMITLESS monitor can be processed and we can configure the network to better react until congestion. The testbed has been built in a HPC cluster using an InfiniBand-based interconnection network. In this system, we have generated realistic traffic scenarios where congestion appears (using well-known benchmarks), and we have analyzed the behavior of our proposal (implemented in OpenSM) compared to the baseline configuration. In the following, we detail the testbed, the performed experiments, and the obtained results.

A. Hardware testbed configuration

CELLIA (Cluster for the Evaluation of Low-Latency Interconnection Architectures) allows to build network topologies using up to 50 HP Proliant DL120 Gen9 server nodes, with a processor Intel Xeon E5-2630v3 8-cores at 1.80 GHz and 16 GB of RAM. The interconnection network is built with IBA-based hardware². CELLIA has up to 50 Mellanox IS5022 8-port switches with QDR technology, each port offering 40 Gbps, which can be used to build different network topologies. Specifically, We use QSFP copper cables with 4x QDR links. Each server node has a dual-port Mellanox ConnectX3 MCX353A-QCBT HCA with 40 Gbps.

We have built in CELLIA, a 36-node 3-stage slimmed fat-tree³ (SFT) [11]. The SFT is a very well-known topology, due to its popularity and widespread use in HPC systems. Figure 2 shows the SFT topology built in CELLIA.

In order to provide a fair comparison between the default IBA CC and our proposal, we have designed a set of tests using three CC configurations: (1) Without CC (disabled), (2) standard IBA CC (i.e. *static*), and (3) LIMITLESS+CC (i.e., our proposal), which tunes the CC parameters dynamically based on the monitoring information. Table I shows the configuration of the IBA CC parameters.

²Note that CELLIA's network is based on the QDR (i.e., not recent) InfiniBand technology. Nevertheless, this network allows to check the viability and effectiveness of our proof-of-concept implementation. Moreover, our proposal is compatible with more modern InfiniBand hardware, that, as assumed by our approach, still uses a congestion-control mechanism based on injection throttling (see: <https://support.mellanox.com/s/article/Nvidia-Congestion-Control>) and performance counters to collect information about network status (see <https://support.mellanox.com/s/article/understanding-mlx5-linux-counters-and-status-parameters>). Note however that the specific results of our approach for the different InfiniBand technologies could vary quantitatively.

³Additionally, we have evaluated our implementation in a 36-node KNS topology, which has been also built in CELLIA. The descriptions and the experiment results have been included in a supplementary file.

Fig. 2: A 36-node 3-stage slimmed fat-tree (SFT). Green nodes are used in the GPCNeT benchmark to measure performance, while orange nodes are used to generate congestion.

TABLE I: Congestion control and monitor configuration.

	Parameter	Value
Common parameters	<i>Threshold</i>	0x7
	<i>Packet_Size</i>	1
	<i>Marking_Rate</i>	0x000f
	<i>CCTI_Timer</i>	150
	<i>CCTI_Increase</i>	{1,2,5,10,20}
Our proposal's parameters	<i>Upper_limit (see Algorithm 1)</i>	0.850 ms
	<i>Lower_limit (see Algorithm 1)</i>	0.055 ms

Note that we have used different values for *CCTI_Increase* to evaluate how this parameter impacts the node congestion; a high value of *CCTI_Increase* throttles the injection traffic flows more aggressively. The rest of the parameters have been configured as recommended in other studies [1].

B. Network workloads

To measure the network performance under congested scenarios, we have selected and installed in CELLIA two well-known benchmarks: Netgauge [12] and GPCNeT [13]. These benchmarks generate in the network common communication patterns that will allow us to validate the proof-of-concept of our proposal. *Netgauge* is a high-precision network parameter measurement tool, which supports many different network protocols and communication patterns, like efficient bisection bandwidth (*ebb*) or many-to-one (*Nto1*). Specifically, the *ebb* communication pattern measures the effective bisection bandwidth, as defined in [14], by generating several random traffic patterns and computing the bisection bandwidth on those patterns. For the *Nto1* traffic pattern, $N-1$ processes (where $N = 36$ in our cluster) communicate data to a chosen single destination (hot-spot), and it sends data back to them. We have executed Netgauge with 36 MPI tasks (i.e., one MPI task per end node in the cluster).

GPCNeT is generally used to measure the impact of congestion in HPC systems. It has been tested in systems such as Cray or Summit. GPCNeT randomly chooses 20% of the nodes (i.e., the probe nodes) to calculate the performance metrics and the rest of the nodes to generate congesting traffic (i.e., the congestor nodes). We have tweaked GPCNeT so that the probe nodes chosen randomly are the same in the SFT among the different configurations for the *CCTI_Increase* parameter, and to measure accurately the value of the *PortXmitWait* and *PortXmitData* values as a function of time (as we describe later).

Figure 2 shows the probe nodes (in green) and the congestor nodes (in orange). We have run GPCNeT using 8 MPI ranks per node both for both topologies. GPCNeT offers performance metrics by means of several tests:

- *Random Ring Point-to-point Latency (P2P Lat)*. The MPI tasks of the probe nodes are sorted in a Random Ring structure, each task sending 8-Byte messages to a neighbor in the ring and receiving 8-Byte messages from the other neighbor in the ring. Note that in this test, the latency of the packets is measured in microseconds (μs).
- *Random Ring Point-to-point Bandwidth with Synchronization (P2PBW+Sync)*. In the same structure mentioned above, eight 128 KB messages are sent to and received from the left and right neighbours (16 messages in total), which are typically enough messages to achieve peak bandwidth [13]. This test is sensitive to bandwidth contention and latency from the synchronization.
- *AllReduce*. Small (8-Byte) MPI AllReduce operations are executed. This test is used to measure the congestion impact on latency-sensitive collective communication.

In the case of GPCnet, for each test, it runs the algorithms previously described without congestion (the congestor nodes do not generate traffic). Next, those congestors stress the network executing again the same algorithms. We have analyzed the IBA performance counters provided by LIMITLESS for each test of this evaluation.

C. Netgauge results analysis

Figures 3, 4, 5 and 6 show the experimental results for the *Nto1* and *ebb* tests of Netgauge using three configurations: no congestion control (“WithoutCC”), standard InfiniBand CC (“CC”) and our proposal (called “LIMITLESS+CC” in the plots). Note that for CC and LIMITLESS+CC several series of results are shown in figures 3 and 5, corresponding to the different values of *CCTI_Increase* (see Table I). Figure 3 shows the throughput results (measured in Mbit/s) when the *Nto1* test of Netgauge is run using different MPI message size. Although there are no significant variations between the different configurations, “LIMITLESS+CC” achieves similar performance regardless of the value of *CCTI_increase* for messages smaller than 4K (where *CCTI_increase* 1 achieves a slight improvement), and the best performance at large message sizes for most values of *CCTI_increase*, compared to the “Without CC” and “CC” configurations. Note also that the *Nto1* traffic pattern does not generate victim flows (i.e., all the traffic flows are congesting).

Figure 4 shows the performance counters values in node 30 versus time during the execution time of the *Nto1* test (around 22 seconds). We have set the *CCTI_Increase* parameter to 5, which is an intermediate value making the injection throttling more sensitive to network traffic status. Specifically, the *PortXmitData* values (i.e., the injection rate) are similar for the three CC configurations, since the *Nto1* traffic pattern does not generate victim flows. The *PortXmitWait* results, measured in ms, show that, when we use “LIMITLESS+CC”, the packets are waiting to be injected a period of time significantly shorter,

(a) CC.

(b) LIMITLESS+CC.

Fig. 3: Network Throughput for the Netgauge *Nto1* communication pattern (MBit/s) versus packet size (Bytes) in logarithmic scale. *CCTI_Increase* is set to 1, 2, 5, 10 and 20. The “WithoutCC” series are identical in both plots.

(a) *PortXmitData* in node30

(b) *PortXmitWait* in node30

Fig. 4: Results for the *PortXmitData* and *PortXmitWait* performance counters in node 30 with the *Nto1* communication pattern versus Time (*CCTI_Increase* = 5).

(a) ebb CC.

(b) ebb LIMITLESS+CC.

Fig. 5: Network Throughput for the Netgauge *ebb* communication pattern (MBit/s) versus packet size (Bytes) in logarithmic scale. *CCTI_Increase* parameter is set to 1, 2, 5, 10 and 20.

meaning that the injection throttling (i.e., the IRD value) is adjusted more precisely when congestion appears.

Figures 5 and 6 show the experimental results for the

Netgauge *ebb* communication pattern. Note that *ebb* generates traffic flows whose destination is chosen randomly following a uniform distribution. Hence, the *ebb* test does

(a) *PortXmitData* in node30.

(b) *PortXmitWait* in node30.

Fig. 6: *PortXmitData* (MB/s) and *PortXmitWait* (ms) values in node 30 with the *ebb* communication pattern versus Time (*CCTI_Increase* = 5).

not generate long-lived congestion situations. As we can see in Figure 5, there is a significant performance degradation when CC is configured with higher *CCTI_Increase* values. By contrast, LIMITLESS+CC shows no performance variations regardless the value of the *CCTI_Increase* parameter. Hence, LIMITLESS+CC widens the range of suitable values for the *CCTI_Increase* parameter.

Figure 6 shows a typical case of injection rate oscillations in the nodes. Note that the the number of milliseconds waiting to send data (i.e., the *PortXmitWait* values) barely increases over 1ms, which means that congestion is not really spoiling the network performance in this scenario. Thus, it is not desirable to enable the CC mechanism under such a situation of light congestion without any impact on the network performance. However, note that as this is not a choice for the network administrator, then enabling our proposal better handles light congestion compared to the traditional CC mechanism. If the CC is used, it triggers immediately the throttling of the traffic flows generating the light congestion, even though this congestion is not dangerous. Although there are oscillations in the *PortXmitData* results for “LIMITLESS+CC” its performance in this scenario is similar to “Without CC” and “CC”, since light congestion does not spoil the network performance.

D. GPCNeT results analysis

Table II shows the results for the GPCNeT P2PBW+Sync test. We focus on this test since we are interested in the bandwidth results. Note that the CELLIA cluster facility is small compared to largest supercomputers in the world (where GPCNeT has been and run and it results has been published in the past). It is worth mentioning that the LIMITLESS+CC implementation proposed in this work is a proof-of-concept to demonstrate that our proposal is able to leverage the monitoring information, and to avoid the traditional IBA CC mechanism overreaction when congestion is light or inaccuracy when congestion is strong.

Table II shows in green those table cells where LIMITLESS+CC outperforms CC. Our proposal outperforms many

TABLE II: Average (Avg) and 99-th tile (99th) GPCNeT P2PBW+Sync results (MiB/s/rank), using IBA CC and LIMITLESS+CC (LIM+CC) and the speedup percentage compared to “Without CC” (in parentheses).

		CCTI Increase Values					Without CC	
		1	5	10	20			
GPCNeT With Cong. (P2P BW)	Avg.	CC	76.2 (-0.26%)	82.6 (8.12%)	77.5 (1.44%)	85.7 (12.17%)	82.3 (7.72%)	76.4
		LIM+CC	80.5 (5.37%)	75.6 (-1.05%)	79.2 (3.66%)	76.2 (-0.26%)	78.9 (3.27%)	
	99th	CC	63.2 (0%)	63.9 (1.11%)	62.2 (-1.58%)	68.1 (7.75%)	62.9 (-0.47%)	63.2
		LIM+CC	65.8 (4.11%)	62.7 (-0.79%)	64.6 (2.22%)	59.6 (-5.7%)	63.2 (0%)	
GPCNeT Without Cong. (P2P BW)	Avg.	CC	200.2 (-0.15%)	146.6 (-26.88%)	183.4 (-8.53%)	137.3 (-31.52%)	159.3 (-20.55%)	200.5
		LIM+CC	170.4 (-15.01%)	177.2 (-11.62%)	181.3 (-9.58%)	173 (-13.72%)	170 (-15.21%)	
	99th	CC	167.4 (1.33%)	122.2 (-26.03%)	153.9 (-6.84%)	118.9 (-28.03%)	130.5 (-21%)	165.2
		LIM+CC	131.1 (-20.64%)	142 (-14.04%)	123.9 (-25%)	137.3 (-16.89%)	133.1 (-19.43%)	

times CC no matter if there is light congestion (“Without Cong.” rows in the table) or strong congestion (“With Cong.” rows in the table). More precisely, LIMITLESS+CC outperforms IBA CC 65% if we compare the green cells in Table II and the same Table for the KNS topology included in the supplementary file. When there is congestion in the network our proposal outperforms both the CC and Without CC configurations for *CCTI_Increase* values of 1 and 5, in both the Average and 99th-tile tests. Note the CC mechanism also outperforms the Without CC baseline case for the Average case, while for the 99th-tile case the performance gain diminishes. This means that the CC does not deal equally long-lived congesting flows. The LIMITLESS+CC results remain consistent (i.e., with small variations) regardless the *CCTI_Increase* values. As we have mentioned above, LIMITLESS+CC reduces the overreaction of the InfiniBand CC mechanism when the congestion is light.

Figure 7 shows the results for the *PortXmitData* (in GB/s) and *PortXmitWait* (in milliseconds waited in average to send data) performance counters values, obtained when running the complete GPCNeT benchmark. During the execution of GPCNeT, first, the P2P Lat test is run, then the P2PBW+Sync and finally the AllReduce test. These tests last around 40

seconds, and they only generate traffic in the probe nodes (i.e., those colored in green in Figure 2). After this period of time, the congestor nodes (i.e., the ones colored in orange in Figure 2) generate strong congestion. The *PortXmitData* results show that, when there is no congestion (i.e., before 40 seconds), “LIMITLESS+CC” configuration reaches a peak performance of 800 MB/s the best outperforming both the “CC” and the “WithoutCC” configurations. Note that the *PortXmitWait* values range from 0 to 0.5 ms in this scenario.

Furthermore, when congestion starts after 40 seconds, the amount of traffic delivered by the network is reduced to 300 MB/s, as shown by the *PortXmitData* values. Note that congestor nodes (80% as defined by GPCNet) generate a big amount of traffic, so that congestion impacts on the overall network performance and makes the GPCNet tests to last for more time. On the other hand, the values for the *PortXmitWait* indicate that the time waited to send data for the “LIMITLESS+CC”, “CC” and “WithoutCC” configurations significantly increases (up to 2.5ms) when congestion appears, but there is also more traffic injected in the network compared to the “CC” mechanism, since the latter mechanism always reacts behind the schedule to congestion, allowing the injection of traffic from congesting sources when it should throttle them.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

We have extended the OpenSM control software of IBA networks to use fine-grain monitoring information and configured the IBA congestion control (CC) to operate with higher accuracy. Our proposal enables OpenSM to dynamically configure the IBA CC parameters in runtime, so that server nodes do not overreact throttling the traffic flows unnecessarily. We have evaluated our proposal in a real cluster by running widely used micro-benchmarks to stress the network, such as NetGauge and GPCNet, which are widely used to measure the congestion impact in high-speed interconnects. The results show that our proposal reduces the overreaction of the CC mechanism regardless of the congestion severity while easing the configuration of the corresponding parameters. In future work, we plan to extend our proposal with distributed processing of collected information directly at the HCAs, leaving the OpenSM intervention to more general aspects and accelerating the reaction of our proposal.

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(a) *PortXmitData* in node30.

(b) *PortXmitWait* in node30.

Fig. 7: GPCNeT Results versus Time for the *PortXmitData* and *PortXmitData* performance counters. Congestion starts after 40 seconds ($CCTI_Increase = 5$).

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